

Thermal Diffusion of Water in Clays

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Thermal diffusion of water in sodium bentonite and kaolinite has been studied, and the results interpreted in terms of the theories of irreversible thermodynamics. The role of heat of transport in characterising the clay-water interactions, as emphasised elsewhere, has been highlighted, and its variations with the nature of the clay, as well as its moisture content and C.E.C., investigated. The results agree, on a qualitative level, with the predicted trends.

IN the background of a number of isolated studies¹ on the thermal diffusion (of mostly water) in soil, most of which have been dealt with by rather *ad hoc* theoretical treatments, Taylor and Cary²⁻⁴ first made an attempt to treat such coupled transport processes in soil in terms of the generalised theories of irreversible thermodynamics. Since then, Tripathi and Ghildyal⁵ and others have worked on Indian soils also in similar lines. But the qualitative aspects of these thermal diffusion studies have received very little attention thus far. Recently, Sanyal and Adhikari^{6,7} have discussed the significance of quantities, such as heat and entropy of transport, and transported entropy of the diffusing soil water (hitherto largely unemphasised upon for soil systems), in characterising the soil moisture-interactions and also conducted experiments, covering these aspects, on non-isothermal transport of water through soil⁸. The present paper extends such thermal diffusion studies (of water) to clays by following a method which is essentially the same as that used by Cary and Taylor^{2,3}, even though the treatment of data has been different according to a method suggested by Sanyal *et al.*⁸. The latter is evidently simpler in that it obviates some steps in the experimental methodology of Cary and Taylor. Furthermore, the heat of transport of clay water (\hat{Q}_w) has been calculated by fitting the experimental data to such modified equations, and qualitative information regarding clay-water interactions is derived therefrom.

Theoretical

The essential difference between the treatments followed by Sanyal *et al.*^{6,7} and Cary and Taylor^{2,3}

is that the former works in terms of an entropy flux, J_s (in addition to the clay water-flux, J_w), while the latter used an energy-flux, J_u . The two can be related by equation⁹ (1).

$$TJ_s = J_u - \mu_w J_w \quad (1)$$

where μ_w is the chemical potential of clay-water.

The quantity, 'transported energy' of clay-water \bar{U}_w , which follows from Cary-Taylor's model (but not introduced or discussed by the authors), is defined to be the amount of total energy-flux associated with a unit isothermal flux of clay-water. The corresponding heat of transport (\hat{Q}_w)^{6,9} is related to the former by equation⁹ (2).

$$\hat{Q}_w = \bar{U}_w - h_w \quad (2)$$

where h_w is the specific enthalpy of clay-water. \hat{Q}_w is sensitive to the nature of clay-water interactions^{6,7}.

The linear phenomenological equations of Taylor and Cary^{2,3} read,

$$\begin{aligned} J_w &= L_{ww} \cdot T \text{ grad } (\mu_w/T) - L_{wu} \cdot \text{grad } T/T \\ J_u &= L_{uw} \cdot T \text{ grad } (\mu_w/T) - L_{uu} \cdot \text{grad } T/T \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Evidently, then $\bar{U}_w = (J_u / J_w) \text{ grad } T = 0$

$$= \frac{L_{uw}}{L_{ww}} \quad (4)$$

By considering a series of substitutions and approximations, and on the assumption that C_p for moist clays has a constant value of $75.3 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (in the temperature range of $0-45^\circ$)¹, Taylor and Cary arrived at the following "Working equations",

$$(J_w)_x = A_w \log T + B_w (1/T) \quad 5(a)$$

$$(J_u)_x = D_u \log T + C_u (1/T) \quad 5(b)$$

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(fluxes in X direction only considered) where the various coefficients are given by,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} A_w &= 9.82 \times 10^{11} L_{ww} \\ B_w &= 5.68 \times 10^8 (L_{wu} - 2.23 \times 10 L_{ww}) \\ C_u &= L_{uu} - 2.23 \times 10^4 L_{uw} \\ D_u &= 173 L_{uw} \end{aligned} \right\} (6)$$

Provided that the fluxes and forces are properly chosen^{6,9}, Onsager's reciprocity relations (O.R.R.) between the cross-effect phenomenological coefficients (representing "coupling" between non-conjugate fluxes and forces) hold good, *i.e.* in this case,

$$L_{wu} = L_{uw} \quad (7)$$

The thermal diffusion runs were conducted in the present case in a three compartment-cell (described with fuller details in the following section) in which the clay chamber was sandwiched between two terminal water compartments. Different temperatures were maintained across the two clay-water boundaries.

The various phenomenological coefficients, and hence the heat of transport of clay-water, were calculated by fitting the data obtained from the present experiments to the following sets of equations suggested by Sanyal *et al*⁸.

If m = mass of water in the hot side chamber,
 s = specific heat of water,

T_3 and T_0 = temperature in the hot chamber and of the surrounding region, respectively, then

$$ms(T_3 - T_0) = Q_{\text{surrounding}} + Q_{\text{clay}} \quad (8)$$

where the quantities Q_j denoted the amount of 'heat loss' to the sinks indicated by the respective subscripts (j).

Similarly, if T'_s is the temperature in the hot chamber,

$$ms(T'_s - T_0) = Q'_{\text{sur}} + Q'_{\text{clay}} \quad (9)$$

As a first approximation, it may be assumed, $Q_{\text{sur}} \cong Q'_{\text{sur}}$, provided that T_s and T'_s are close together.

Hence, from equations (8) and (9),

$$ms(T_s - T'_s) = Q_{\text{clay}} - Q'_{\text{clay}} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Now, } Q_{\text{clay}} = TJ_s A \quad (11)$$

where J_s is the flux of entropy through clay, A is the cross sectional area for heat flow, and t is the time for such flow.

Again by using equation (1),

$$(J_u)_1 - (J_u)_2 = (TJ_s)_1 - (TJ_s)_2 + \mu_w [(J_w)_1 - (J_w)_2]$$

Here, $(J_u)_1$ corresponds to (T_s, T_2) gradient, and $(J_u)_2$ to (T'_s, T'_2) gradient, T_2 and T'_2 being the respective cold chamber temperatures in the two cases.

Hence from equation (11),

$$(J_u)_1 - (J_u)_2 = (Q_{\text{clay}} - Q'_{\text{clay}}) / At + \mu_w [(J_w)_1 - (J_w)_2]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i.e., } ms \frac{T_3 - T'_3}{At} + \mu_w [(J_w)_1 - (J_w)_2] \\ = (J_u)_1 - (J_u)_2 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

If the four temperature gradients used for a given clay sample at a definite moisture content are, $T_3, T_2; T'_3, T'_2; T_5, T_4; T'_5, T'_4$, and T_0 = the surrounding temperature, then by using Cary-Taylor's equation (5b), we obtain, (i) for (T_3, T_2) and (T'_3, T'_2) gradient,

$$(J_u)_1 - (J_u)_2 = D_u [\log(T_3/T_2) - \log(T'_3/T'_2)] + C_u [(1/T_3 - 1/T_2) - (1/T'_3 - 1/T'_2)]$$

By using equation (12),

$$\begin{aligned} ms \frac{T_3 - T'_3}{At} + \mu_w [(J_w)_1 - (J_w)_2] \\ = D_u [\log(T_3/T_2) - \log(T'_3/T'_2)] + \\ C_u [(1/T_3 - 1/T_2) - (1/T'_3 - 1/T'_2)] \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

For (T_5, T_4) and (T'_5, T'_4) gradients, an equation, similar to equation (13), may be established, and these two equations may then be solved to yield the values of the coefficients C_u and D_u , provided that J_w, μ_w, t, m, A , and s are known. The clay water chemical potential μ_w may be obtained from the relation, $\psi_w = \mu_w - \mu_w^0$, where ψ_w is the clay water-potential, and μ_w^0 is the chemical potential of pure water (in the standard state). (ii) Following Cary-Taylor's equation (5a), the soil water flux J_w was calculated as,

$$(J_w)_1 - (J_w)_2 = A_w [\log(T_3/T_2) - \log(T'_3/T'_2)] + B_w [(1/T_3 - 1/T_2) - (1/T'_3 - 1/T'_2)] \quad (14)$$

for the temperature gradients (T_3, T_2) and (T'_3, T'_2) .

For temperature gradients (T_5, T_4) and (T'_5, T'_4) , we can write down a similar equation incorporating A_w and B_w ; A_w and B_w may then be obtained by calculations as for C_u and D_u .

A knowledge of A_w, B_w, C_u and D_u , as obtained above, leads to the various phenomenological coefficients from equation (6). Alternatively, the various L coefficients of equation (6) can be determined from A_w, B_w and the assumption that O.R.R. holds good in such coupled transport processes in soil. The latter is justified in view of quite a few pieces of work of this type, verifying O.R.R., and already reported in the literature¹.

Finally, the heat of transport of clay water, \hat{Q}_w , is obtained according to the relation (vide equations 2 and 4),

$$\hat{Q}_w = (L_{uw}/L_{ww}) - h_w = (L_{wu}/L_{ww}) - h_{wg} \quad (15)$$

by using O.R.R. (equation 7).

Knowing h_w , the specific enthalpy of clay water, \hat{Q}_w can thus be evaluated.

Experimental

The diffusion set-up used in the present investigation is basically the same as that of Cary and Taylor²⁻⁴. It consisted of a three-chamber perspex box (Fig. 1) in which the clay compartment was sandwiched between the terminal water-chambers.

The latter were maintained at different temperatures by having incorporated in them heating and cooling arrangements, respectively (Fig. 1), and temperature drops across clay-water boundaries were measured by means of copper-constantan thermocouples. The water-flux through clay in the appropriate direction was ascertained by noting, with the help of a travelling vernier microscope, the displacement of an air-bubble introduced inside a capillary flow tube (an inverted U glass capillary tube), the ends of which were inserted through the perspex lid of the diffusion cell in the terminal water-chambers. The net water-flux in time upto the attainment of the steady state, in ~1 h, was recorded.

Fig. 1.

Experiments were conducted at two moisture contents (field capacity and 50% of it) of each of the two clay samples, sodium bentonite and sodium kaolinite (1 : 2.5 clay : water suspension having pH 8.7 and 7.6, and C.E.C. 74.0 and 13.1 meq. per 100 g of clay, respectively).

These clay samples were obtained by converting the crude bentonite and kaolinite to the H⁺-form by treatment with 0.05 M HCl, followed by removal of the excess chloride on dialysis through cellophane, and subsequent transformation of the H⁺-clays to the Na⁺-form by leaching with 2 M NaCl solution, then washing with distilled water, and finally dialysed.

Results and Discussion

The data obtained from various calculations, as elaborated in the section on theory, are presented in Tables 1 and 2. Table 2 records the various L-coefficients obtained from A_w, B_w coefficients of equation 6 (which, in turn, are recorded in Table 1 for the clay samples at different moisture contents), and an application of O.R.R. The \hat{Q}_w values of water in clays at varying degrees of saturation are summarised in Table 2.

An increase in \hat{Q}_w with moisture content, as observed with both Na-bentonite and Na-kaolinite, is in qualitative agreement with the theoretical considerations, presented elsewhere⁷, that with the growth of structured water region around the clay particles (with an accompanying increase in moisture content), \hat{Q}_w is expected to increase. Such a variation is seen to be much more marked with bentonite than with kaolinite. This possibly arises from a much stronger bonding of bentonite surfaces (swelling type, higher C.E.C.) for water at low moisture contents than that of kaolinite at more or less similar moisture contents; the latter causes the

TABLE 1—DATA OBTAINED FROM 'THERMAL DIFFUSION' EXPERIMENT ACROSS CLAY SAMPLES

Clay Sample	Moisture %	Temperature of		Displacement of bubble/cm*	A _w	B _w			
		Hot chamber T/°C	Cold chamber T/°C						
Na-Bentonite	56	33.09	25.91	0.3	37.0	1370.0			
		33.31	25.96	0.1					
		33.49	27.43	0.4					
		37.65	29.67	0.2					
	28	28.57	25.18	0.3	50.0	442.0			
		30.79	26.33	0.6					
		31.99	26.40	0.4					
		32.94	27.94	0.3					
		35.98	26.98	0.7					
		37.98	28.47	0.4					
46	36.48	26.28	1.0	405.4	8350.0				
	37.05	26.33	0.8						
	Na-Kaolinite	23	36.88			27.38	0.6	73.6	585.0
			37.93			27.68	0.9		
38.32			28.17	1.1					
39.12			28.57	0.8					

* Accuracy of measurements within ±0.005 cm.

TABLE 2—PHENOMENOLOGICAL COEFFICIENTS AND HEAT OF TRANSPORT OF CLAY-WATER
(OBTAINED FROM ANALYSIS OF THE DATA OF TABLE 1)

Sample	Moisture %	$L_{ww} \times 10^{10} / \text{J mol}^2 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$L_{wu} \times 10^6 / \text{mol cm}^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1}$	Heat of transport* $\hat{Q}_w = [(L_{wu} / L_{ww}) - h_w] \times 10^{-1} \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$
Na-Bentonite	56	3.77	1.08	2.86
	28	5.09	1.21	2.37
Na-Kaolinite	46	41.2	10.67	2.57
	23	7.49	1.77	2.35

* Value of h_w , 113.61 J mol⁻¹ at 33°, noted from "Handbook of Chemistry Physics", C. R. C. Press, 1975-76, pp. D-158.

partial migration (of only layer A) of the ordered clay-water zones to appreciably change over to an *en bloc* migration at lower moisture in case of bentonite, and not to an equal extent, at least, in kaolinite. This leads to a sharper decrease of \hat{Q}_w at lower moisture content for bentonite^{6,7}.

A greater \hat{Q}_w at high moisture content (field capacity moisture) for bentonite obviously stems from a larger inter-layer surface area (of high charge density), exposed to water, in bentonite than in kaolinite. The values get closer together at lower moisture (50% of field capacity moisture), and may be interpreted in terms of the aforesaid strong bonding of bentonite surfaces for water as compared to the corresponding situation in kaolinite at lower moisture.

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